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**Money in the Digital Age and
Crypto-Assets : What Challenges and
Opportunities for Central Banks?**

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Digital Currencies: What Transformations Should Be Expected in Europe?

Following the announcement in 2019 of the creation of a stablecoin by the Meta group, so-called “stable cryptocurrencies” have emerged with the aim of decentralising money by bypassing traditional supervisory authorities. These financial innovations raise new challenges regarding the European monetary anchor. Consequently, central bankers are now considering a new form of central bank digital money.

The Euro in Light of Contemporary Challenges

The entry into the digital era as early as 2008, followed by Meta’s Libra project launched in 2019, provided the momentum for central bank digital currencies (CBDCs) in Western economies. Central banks, as supervisory institutions and vectors of trust in money, are the issuers of public money. Money is a stable-value asset used as a medium of exchange, endowed with legal tender status and based on trust. Public money is traditionally available in the form of cash (coins and banknotes) for individuals, and reserves for financial institutions. Private money, by contrast, corresponds to scriptural money (bank cards, transfers, etc.). These forms of money serve as means of payment.

Figure 1: Annualised volatility rates compared across different asset classes (in %)

Source: Banque de France (2020); Kaiko, Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, and Kaiko calculations

Privately initiated currencies designed to bypass financial institutions—particularly for international settlements or peer-to-peer transactions—escape central bank oversight. This is the case for so-called “cryptocurrencies.” However, they do not meet the definitional criteria of money, especially in the case of coins. This is due to their high volatility and the absence of legal tender status, which prevent them from being considered genuine means of payment. They are instead risky digital and cryptographic assets, making the term “crypto-assets” more appropriate. Stablecoins—a sub-category of crypto-assets with relatively stable value because they are backed by reserves composed of stable assets (Treasury bills, gold, demand deposits)—emerged in 2014 in order to function as genuine means of payment. Figure 1 suggests significantly higher volatility for coins (Bitcoin, Ether, Ripple) than for stablecoins (Paxos Standard, TrueUSD, Tether). Indeed, between November 2019 and May 2020, Bitcoin’s median volatility reached 80%, compared with approximately 2% for Tether.

The digital euro project originated from an initiative by six European banks, including the Banque de France, at the beginning of the 2020s. One of its objectives is to counter the ongoing process of monetary decentralisation. The digital euro is expected to rely on a two-tier infrastructure. On the one hand, there will be a retail digital euro, usable by individuals at points of sale (POS) or online. On the other hand, there will be a wholesale digital euro, used for inter-state transactions by actors authorised by the European Central Bank (ECB) and based on a cryptographic (blockchain) architecture. Any euro would be convertible into digital euro within a predefined holding limit, and vice versa.

A European Sovereignty Issue

Figure 2: Distribution of payment methods at POS in the euro area (as % of transactions)

Source: ECB, SUCH survey (2016) and SPACE surveys (2019, 2022, and 2024)

The SPACE survey presented in Figure 2 shows that the share of cash used as a means of payment at POS in the euro area declined by 27 percentage points between 2016 and 2024. The same study indicates that 2023 marked a turning point in cash usage in favour of digital payment instruments. However, these private payment instruments are not guaranteed by central bank authority, which could undermine internal monetary sovereignty and the European monetary anchor. If they were to become entrenched, they would weaken the “monetary policy transmission mechanism” ([BCE, 2024](#)). International card payments schemes—such as Mastercard or Visa—are already firmly established in Europe, accounting for 61% of card transactions in 2022 ([BCE, 2025](#)). This raises questions about the European Union’s ability to preserve its internal monetary sovereignty.

Beyond the emergence of private payment instruments, the rise of “stable value tokens” is reshaping relations between national economies and the International Monetary System (IMS) by weakening the external monetary sovereignty of certain states. The greater the role of dollar-pegged stablecoins in international transactions, the higher the probability that the dollar’s international dominance will be reinforced. This phenomenon is referred to as “crypto-mercantilism”. Indeed, emerging economies—whose populations are more inclined to adopt private digital currencies due to the instability of their national currencies—may increasingly adopt the dollar in the form of stablecoins, thereby eroding part of their state’s monetary sovereignty ([Monnet & Al., 2025](#)). A downgrading of the euro’s role within the IMS could occur if Europe fails to respond to this crypto-mercantilism ([ibid.](#)). Had Libra, the dollar-pegged stablecoin project, not failed, it could have substituted for the volatile currencies of fragile economies ([Duval, 2024](#)).

The Digital Euro: An Opportunity to Strengthen the Single Currency?

A new responsibility of the ECB would be to regulate the supply of payment instruments in order to prevent the lasting establishment of foreign private means of payment in Europe. This constitutes one of the core rationales for the digital euro. The retail component would help restore balance by acting on the supply side of payment instruments. Through this competitive innovation—designed so that pre-existing payment systems can coexist—the digital euro would offer a new means of payment modelled on cash. It would be issued by the central bank, free of charge, liquid, anonymous, instantly usable, and operable offline ([ECB, 2024](#)). Europeans would thus be able to choose between physical cash, digital cash, and various private payment instruments.

The circulation of a wholesale digital euro would enhance competition with the dollar in cross-border payments. This would involve the development of a blockchain-based system enabling interoperability among national central bank digital currencies. Exchanges between national digital currencies integrated into the system would be secured by distributed ledger technology, which ensures transparency, reliability, and security in financial transactions. Currency hierarchy struggles would be mitigated by the safeguard provided by the wholesale digital euro, acting as a bulwark against crypto-mercantilism ([Monnet & Al., 2025](#)). By preserving the monetary sovereignty of fragile economies integrated into the system, it would strengthen its position vis-à-vis US-backed stablecoins.

Figure 3: The role of the Banque de France: offering a new form of central bank money

Source: Extract from Denis Beau's presentation slides, "What Future for the World of Crypto-Assets?", 2024

“Only a Widely Accepted Digital Euro Can Make a Difference”?

Trust in the euro among Europeans has never been higher. Eighty-three percent of respondents in the euro area report confidence in the single currency ([European Commission, 2025](#)). Whether this trust will extend to a new form of the euro remains to be confirmed. Two members of the Executive Board suggest that “only a widely accepted digital euro [could] make a difference” ([Lagarde & Panetta, 2022](#)). The success of the project therefore appears to depend on the degree of trust and acceptance granted to it by Europeans. To fully complete European integration while addressing sovereignty challenges, the dissemination of an information campaign targeting all stakeholders involved in the digital euro project seems necessary. With the retail digital euro expected around 2028, a strong communication effort is anticipated—similar to that undertaken in the early 2000s.

Bibliographical Appendix

European Central Bank. *Annual Report 2024* (translated). Frankfurt, ECB, 2024, pp. 61–62;

<https://www.ecb.europa.eu/press/annual-reports-financial-statements/annual/html/ecb.ar2024~8402d8191f.en.html#:~:text=At%20the%20start%20of%202024%20the%20ECB%20was.to%20our%20medium-term%20target%20of%202%25%20in%202025> [last access: 17/07/2025];

European Central Bank. *Report on Card Payment Schemes and Processors* (translated). Frankfurt, ECB, 2025, pp. 1 & 5;

<https://www.ecb.europa.eu/pub/pdf/other/ecb.reportcardschemes202502~1614226b0a.en.pdf>

Duval, Maxime. *Public Money in the Digital Age: An Institutionalist Analysis of Central Bank Digital Currencies*. PhD thesis, Université Paris Nanterre, 2024, p. 78;

<https://bdr.parisnanterre.fr/theses/internet/2024/2024PA100069/2024PA100069.pdf> [last access: 17/07/2025];

European Commission. *Standard Eurobarometer 103 – Spring 2025*. Brussels, 2025, p. 27;

<https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/api/deliverable/download/file?deliverableId=98482> [last access: 17/07/2025];

Lagarde, Christine & Panetta, Fabio. *Key Objectives of the Digital Euro* (translated). ECB Blog, 2022, p. 2;

<https://fundamentaltrends.com/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/Key-objectives-of-the-digital-euro.pdf> [last access: 17/07/2025];

Monnet, Eric; Van't Klooster, Jens; Martino, Edoardo David. *Cryptomercantilism vs. Monetary Sovereignty*. Report, 2025, p. 26.

<https://media.licdn.com/dms/document/media/v2/D4E1FAQFccjSlqL6cqA/feedshare-document-pdf-analyzed/B4EZeC7SowHgAc-/0/1750248273922?e=1753315>

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access: 17/07/2025].